

Supplementary Figure 1. Uncropped chemiluminescent blots for PTPRC (upper band) and TUBB (lower band) as loading control upon miR-363-3p inhibition in T-ALL cell lines. **[A, B]** Western Blot for DND-41 cell line transduced with miRZip scrambled vector (lanes 1, 3, 5) and miRZip miR-363-3p vector (lanes 2, 4, 6) with shorter **[A]** and longer **[B]** exposition time, in three biological and two technical replicates. **[C]** Western Blot for ALL-SIL cell line transduced with miRZip scrambled vector (lanes 1, 3, 6) and miRZip miR-363-3p vector (lanes 2, 4, 5) in three biological.

Supplementary Figure 2. Uncropped chemiluminescent blots for SOCS2 (lower band) and TUBB (upper band) as loading control upon miR-363-3p inhibition in T-ALL cell lines. **[A]** Western Blot for DND-41 cell line transduced with miRZip scrambled vector (lanes 1, 3, 5) and miRZip miR-363-3p vector (lanes 2, 4, 6) in three biological and two technical replicates. **[B]** Western Blot for ALL-SIL cell line transduced with miRZip scrambled vector (lanes 1, 3, 5) and miRZip miR-363-3p vector (lanes 2, 4, 6) in three biological.

Supplementary Figure 3. The comparison of relapse occurrence between patient samples clustered based on the expression of JAK-STAT related genes [Fig. 6A]. 0 – no relapse; 1 – relapse. The comparison of relapse occurrence between CL1 **[A]** and CL2 **[B]** patient clusters.

A

B

C

A

B

A
 $\chi^2_{\text{Pearson}}(1) = 1.85, p = 0.17, \hat{V}_{\text{Cramer}} = 0.13, \text{CI}_{95\%} [0.00, 1.00], n_{\text{obs}} = 48$
B
 $\chi^2_{\text{Pearson}}(2) = 1.86, p = 0.40, \hat{V}_{\text{Cramer}} = 0.00, \text{CI}_{95\%} [0.00, 1.00], n_{\text{obs}} = 48$
